

The Expansion of Spacetime as the Basis for Light, Motion, and Time

A Thought Experiment for Theoretical Physics

Summary

This document presents a hypothesis that the expansion of spacetime is not only responsible for the cosmological growth of the universe but also underpins our perception of light, motion, and time. Instead of viewing light as an actively moving entity, it proposes that light may be static, with its energy transported through spacetime expansion.

This perspective may help bridge central questions in cosmology and quantum mechanics, providing new ways to interpret phenomena such as the dual nature of light and the linear perception of time.

Key Ideas of the Hypothesis

Light and Spacetime Expansion

Light might be static. The energy we perceive as the motion of light could be transported towards us through the expansion of spacetime. This perspective might explain the dual nature of light (wave-particle duality) by reinterpreting the observed 'motion' of light.

Motion as a Result of Expansion

Motion is not independent of spacetime but a product of the continuous expansion of the universe. Mass determines how strongly an object 'resists' spacetime expansion. Large masses slow down their relative motion due to expansion (similar to black holes), while smaller masses are carried along faster, potentially explaining abrupt quantum movements.

Time as an Emergent Property

The linear perception of time arises from the continuous expansion of spacetime. Without this expansion, neither motion nor the perception of time would be possible.

Visualization of the Hypothesis

The universe can be imagined as a continuously moving treadmill: objects with large mass remain relatively stable due to their gravitational influence. Smaller masses are carried along faster, affecting their mobility and speed.

Potential Implications

Macroscopic Scale

The hypothesis could extend our understanding of the role of gravity in the expansion of the universe, particularly regarding black holes and dark energy.

Microscopic Scale

It could explain why quantum phenomena, such as wave-particle duality or abrupt particle motion, occur.

Open Questions

- Can this hypothesis be mathematically formulated to complement existing theories such as relativity and quantum mechanics?
- What experimental predictions arise from this perspective that can be tested?
- Is the idea of light being static compatible with current measurements of the speed of light and the cosmic microwave background?

Goal of this Document

This hypothesis is not a complete physical model but a thought experiment intended to inspire scientists to explore new ideas. It is presented for discussion to gather feedback, critique, and potential further development by experts.

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